

Varicose Veins: What You Need To Know?

If you suffer from large and pronounced veins showing just under the surface of your skin, then you need to find a place that specializes in varicose **vein treatment in texas**. You don't have to live with those unsightly blemishes for the rest of your life. If you are surprised about their growth, you need to understand that they are very common to develop in any gender. They are more likely to develop from pregnancy, genetics, being overweight, and from standing for extended periods of time. Even if you develop them, there is a way you can get rid of them by getting **vein treatment in the city center**.

What are the common signs and symptoms?

There are some common signs and symptoms you should look for if you think you have developed weak valves and veins. They appear bluish in color and can be seen through the skin. You may experience swelling, burning, pain, and itching in the legs. You may only notice these symptoms while you are used to standing or sitting for a long time. In more severe cases, there may also be bleeding when scratches and minor injuries occur. Although this condition is not known to cause serious health complications, in rare cases, it can be indicative of a more serious condition called deep vein thrombosis. With the right varicose [vein treatment river oaks](#), you can reduce their appearance and stop the symptoms from occurring.

Take some time to find the right **vein specialist near me**. It doesn't matter how many different home remedies you have tried, the best way to get rid of them is to have the right varicose **veins treatment near me**. In addition to surgery being an option, you may be a good candidate for laser therapy and sclerotherapy for the right **vein treatment in texas**.

Your **vein doctor city center** will be able to assess your condition and determine which option is right for you.

How to alleviate the symptoms?

There are ways you can alleviate your symptoms until you have had surgery. Get more exercise, drink more water, wear compression garments and elevate your legs while you are resting. Before you get surgery, make sure you understand all that is involved with the procedure. Unlike other forms of surgery, you do not need to take a large amount of time off from work.

What are the common prevention measures?

There are also things you can do to lessen your chances of developing weak veins.

- Avoid standing in the same condition for long periods of time. If your job requires you to stand or sit for extended periods of time, take breaks, bend and flex your legs periodically.
- Take a brief walk and allow the blood to circulate to return to your legs. Try to maintain a healthy weight.
- People who are overweight have a higher chance of developing the condition.
- Exercise more and consider swimming and riding a bike. If you do suspect that you have them, don't wait too long before you seek out **varicose vein treatment near me river oaks**.
- Talk with our primary doctor and ask them for a referral to a [vein specialist near me Houston](#).

Contact your health insurer and find out which **vein treatment river oaks** are covered under your plan.